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Examination Malpractice and Failure in West African Examination Council (WAEC) English Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE): Exposure as a Remedy

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews examination malpractice and failure in the West African Examinations Council (WAEC), with particular reference to English Language paper, focusing on the inadequate exposure of candidates to the nature of the examination. It is observed that Many candidates lack orientation on WAEC's structure, marking scheme, and notorious sections such as essay writing, that often, comprehension and summary that determine performance,.This gap in preparation contributes to heavy reliance on malpractice and persistent mass failure. The paper argues that structured guidance, candidate orientation, and teacher-led exposure to WAEC standards would minimise irregularities, reduce failure rates, and restore confidence in the system. It concludes that equipping students with prior knowledge of the examination's expectations is a key solution to malpractice and poor performance.

Keywords: examination malpractice, English Language paper, failure, WAEC

INTRODUCTION

Performance in Senior School Certificate Examination in English in Nigeria, except for some isolated years, recently, has not been very encouraging. Even the years within which performance spectacularly rose, findings of some researches put the performance to question. According to Agwu (2023c) the importance placed on passing the SSCE has led to academic corruption in many forms including the rise of miracle centres (MECs). MECs are schools where candidates by design of some syndicates get undeserving excellent results. Not only malpractice in public examination has taken different shapes: stealing answers from fellow examinees, introduction of unauthorised materials, inflating examination scores or generally abusing the set standard (Agwu-etal 2023) has become the order of the day.

Okoye & Onwuzuruoha, (2020) lament that a network of school actors including teachers, students, parents, school administration and Ministry of Education officials and the examination bodies themselves collude to compromise examination standards set. This unwholesome connivance gives candidates false grades.

Ekkot (2023) in an 8-year review of the WAEC results indicated that improved pass rate was driven by rampant Examination malpractice. Thus, according to him, it was noticeable that between 2015-2023 the pass rate grew from 53% to 79%. Further, WAEC during the same period reported that the results it seized on suspicion of examination malpractice rose from 8.9% to 16.3%. The peak of pass rate of 89% was recorded in 2021 coinciding also with the rate of cheating reaching 22.8% (Ekot 2023).

No wonder as Agwu (2023) laments the trend discourages hardworking students from seriously concentrating on their studies and raising question to the creditability of the certificates issued in Nigeria. This phenomenon therefore raises serious concern especially among stakeholders in Education. Though examination malpractice is not peculiar to secondary schools final examination, the value of SSCE as a pre-requisite for entry into tertiary institutions and the professions pose serious threat to the development of the education sector.

Universities and other tertiary institutions in Nigeria are continually expressing worry about the kind of students transited from secondary to them. The SSCE examination results presented by students for admission are no longer reliable. The credits used to admit the students are losing credence since the owners can practically not defend them.

Several efforts have been put toward curbing the problem by the examination bodies. These include cancelation, with holding of results, legal action against culprits, dismissal of their staff involved etc. Government on its parts has enacted laws against Examination Malpractice to discourage the menace, but with every little result to show. Something tangible therefore ought to be done urgently to save the dangerous situation which can or has seriously affected the education system in Nigeria. This is even so as secondary education plays a pivotal role in the system.

Many factors have played significant role in painting the situation explained above. These may include poor background of the students emanating from poor or non-supply of qualified teachers of English. Others may include poor teaching facilities, negative attitudes of both teachers and students to teaching and learning of English (Umar, 2015). One factor which however stands out is the inherent difficulty and absurdity of the English language (Ikidden, 1985). Also, students generally have developed fear of the SSCE. (Umar, 2015)

To reduce this fear therefore there is need to expose the potential candidates including some of the teachers, especially those who are new or have no experience in the mode of WAEC SSCE English test structure and assessment. This, it is felt, can reduce the attendant tension potential candidates face as the examination approaches resulting in devising different means of circumventing both the process and the examination rules by candidates and their syndicates.

West African Examination Council (WAEC)

The West African Examination Council (WAEC) was first instituted based on the Jeffrey Report resulting in enactment of an ordinance in 1951. The body which was subsequently established in 1952, had its first headquarters in Accra, Ghana (Wikipedia). It metamorphosed into a regional Examination body serving five English West African States. They include Nigeria, Ghana, Sierra Leone, Liberia and the Gambia. The core mandate of WAEC is to conduct exit examination and award certificates not lower in standard than that of the United Kingdom (WAEC) for final year secondary schools students in the aforementioned countries.

Henry Fischel, a philanthropist and business man, was the one to invent Examination in the 19th century (Wikipedia). The first Examination to be conducted was the Imperial Examination in China. The examination was conducted to make a person learn whole things in a night.

Collins Compact English Dictionary (2009) defines examination as a formal test that you take to show your knowledge or ability in a particular subject or to obtain a qualification. WAEC, in Nigeria, conducts the Senior School Certificate Examination for final year students of the second tier of secondary school, the senior secondary school, normally completed in three years after junior secondary. It also issues certificates to the deserving students. The certificates are used for entry into higher education institutions and the professions. The Examination is conducted twice in a year, first in April/may tagged, May/June, and second in September/November, tagged November/December. The first, tagged school examination, and the latter, private candidates. The scripts of the candidates are marked by qualified examiners recruited from universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education, however majority from secondary schools. Normally the results are released to anxious candidates one month after the exercise.

This paper therefore intends to highlight the structure and demands of the WAEC English Language Examination. Most of what is going to be discussed is as a result of several years of personal experience examining, moderating and marking of the WAEC'S English Language Papers.

Structure of WAEC English Language Examination

- I.** English Language 1 - This paper consists of tests in essay, letter writing, comprehension and summary
- II.** English Language 2 - This tests knowledge of structural and lexical items.
- III.** English Language 3 - This tests the basic elements relevant to the understanding of the production and articulation of English Language sounds. It covers the following areas:
 - a) Listening comprehension and recognition test
 - b) Production test- this includes sentence stress, intonation and phrasing.

Marking of WAEC Examination

Of the three papers outlined above, it is only paper 1 that is marked by human hands. Others are marked by different mechanical devices. For paper 1 however, WAEC recruits examiners, most of whom are themselves teachers to set questions, moderate them, draft marking scheme and mark the candidates scripts at different locations in the country.

Stages of Marking

Co-ordination: This exercise is conducted at two or three levels. First, is the national co-ordination where all chief examiners and selected team leaders are oriented and co-ordinated on the draft marking scheme. This produces the final agreed marking scheme to be used at all marking centres in the country for uniformity and quality control. The officers mentioned above, especially chief examiners, and team leaders in turn go to their various marking centres and in a minimum of three days co-ordinate Assistant examiners who will actually mark the life scripts under the strict supervision of these officers.

Vetting: A certain percentage of all scripts marked by examiners is subjected to vigorous vetting to ensure strict adherence to the demands of the marking scheme. This sometimes results in either asking the examiner to remark part or all of the answers or in extreme cases withdrawal of the scripts from further marking by the examiner concerned if found to deviate too much from the approved marking scheme.

Checking: WAEC employs competent persons to particularly check addition of marks to ensure accuracy.

Marking Procedure: Essay and Letter Writing

According to WAEC, these sections test the ability of candidates to use English as an effective means of communication to express themselves with clarity and coherence appropriately. The section presents topics covering a wide variety of writing skills-argument, narrative, exposition, description and imaginative writing all carefully selected to fall within the candidate's experience or knowledge.

Positive Marking: WAEC, generally, emphasizes the principle of positive marking i.e giving credit first for what the candidate has done right and then penalize errors made as stipulated by the marking scheme.

Qualities Examiners Look for While Marking an Essay

The qualities examiners look for in assessing writing are well defined and grouped into four:

- i. Content
- ii. Organisation
- iii. Expression
- iv. Mechanical accuracy

The first aspect, content, which attracts 10 marks refers to ideas relevant to the central theme and their development. The major problem, as observed over the years which students face is that of development of ideas. Another thing worthy of note here is the length of the essay which affects not only the content but other areas of assessment viz mechanical accuracy and expression. The instruction on the length required is always very clear; 400 words for essay and 300 words for letter. The assumption is that the

candidate should be able to express all relevant ideas adequately in the number of words allowed. It is because of this, examiners are instructed to before the beginning to mark the writing estimate the length. Where the writing falls far below the number required candidates in most cases do not perform well. This is because the maximum mark for M.A is proportionately reduced and ideas expressed found too inadequately, thus affecting marks for content as well. Similarly, though there is no stipulated penalty for unnecessarily appreciably longer than required essays, candidates end up including irrelevant ideas and worse still frustrating the examiner the consequences, of which tell much on the final score of the candidates.

The points to look for under the second aspect, organization, which attracts the same marks on content, include, a suitable opening, adequate development, good paragraph and links between paragraphs, balance, unity, coherence and suitable conclusion. Paragraphing and links between and among paragraphs and sentences make for balance, unity and coherence. This is achieved by using suitable paragraphs and sentence connectors such as: moreover, similarly, in addition etc. which connects what has been said before. Another reason, problem, use, advantage, etc. suggest a continuation of thought. However, nevertheless, on the other-hand etc. Suggest contrast with what has gone before.

The paragraph on the whole should help the writer to parcel up his ideas so as to deliver them to the reader one by one in an orderly logical manner or sequence. Let us study the paragraph below.

My boy friend is a generous giver. Such time we go out together, he insists on paying for everything I need. When my money was stolen in the hostel, he gave me N 5000:00 to make up for the loss. Last week he bought an expensive birth day present for me. The week before, he took me out for dinner at one of the most expensive restaurant in town. Although my friend is quite generous, he is not a bright student and he usually copies my work during exams.()

The paragraph looks good on the surface, but something is wrong with it. It discusses more than one idea. The last sentence is out of place.

To achieve suitable opening, candidates should learn to use apt quotations, special but interesting definitions, catchy sentences right from the take-off. Having started off marvelously, the candidate should try to sustain the tempo until the end. The same time the candidates is thinking of a suitable introduction his mind should be set on the conclusion on which he earns much of the marks the essay merits. Again, a benefiting quotation, interesting anecdote or a analogy derived from the body of the essay rightly belongs here, so as to give the essay a tone of finality.

The next area, expressions has always posed a big problem to candidates. Yet it attracts the lion share of 20 marks. It covers areas such as; range and aptness of vocabulary, effective arrangement and variety of sentence structures, judicious and imaginative use of figurative language, and appropriate collocations. It is appalling to note that even essays that are almost error free mechanically, sometimes score very low under this aspect. Candidates should therefore be advised to try to convey their ideas and thoughts in very clear, simple, attractive and intelligible language. The guide here as opined by Blackie (1993) is “ when in doubt about the meaning of a word, phrase or a whole expression, do not use it at all, instead, use a clearer and simple alternative” p20.

Mechanical accuracy, which attracts 10 marks, is the final aspect which examiners look for.

It is concerned with the candidate’s ability to use the mechanics of language correctly. Such mechanics cover punctuation, spelling, tenses and other grammatical aspects.

WAEC Chief Examiners’ Report

Unfortunately, however, MA is one area that seems to pose the greatest difficulty. It is the area that has so far recorded the worst performance. (Chief examinations report). A very significant number of candidates loose all the ten precious marks allotted to this aspect. WAEC Chief Examiners Reports on GCE/SSCE have consistently shown the abysmal performance of student in M.A. One of such reports says:

“The candidates’ performance, however, was generally disappointing especially in the area of expression and mechanical accuracy. There was abundant evidence that most candidates merely translated the vernacular expressions into English.....” WAEC (1984:p11)

WAEC Chief Examiners Report (1987:p30) says it more succinctly:

“The most serious weakness was candidate’s inability to spell and punctuate correctly. This, coupled with inability to write meaningful expressions, caused many candidates loss of many marks”

WAEC chief examiners have consistently lamented candidates’ poor mastery in the SSCE English papers in:

6. Punctuation
7. Spelling
8. Grammar

I say this area poses the greatest difficulty because reports such as those quoted above are usually sent to schools for “further necessary action” by teachers. WAEC on its part has made even deliberate attempts year-in-year out to reduce the number of casualties by reducing the number of areas to be panelized under M.A. For instance, in the past misuse of commas of any type were to be penelised. This is now penelised only in simple structures and similar places. Again in the past, misspelling of the same word however it occurred was to be penelised. Today, it is only to be penelised once. Subsequent occurrences are only noted. A lot of these penalties have been reviewed to give room for scoring more marks in M.A. but to no avail.

As Grieve (1964) opines:

In a situation where English is a second language it is to be expected that the kinds of English found will be different from the variety spoken in countries where English is the mother tongue.

The point about English in Nigeria is not just that there are several varieties of English-ranging from smoothly very near Standard English to the patois of the market place. p

The claim here is that the core reasons for students’ poor performance in the mechanics of English is the status of the language in Nigeria-L2. This brings us to the concept of mother tongue interference. Most of our students are incipient bilinguals. Consequently code transfers, direct translation from L1 to L2 are imminent. These have serious negative effects on their grammar, spelling and punctuation. They think in their mother tongues and transfer their thought directly into English. A few examples will suffice:

- | | | |
|---|---|---------|
| 1. I don’t hear his language | - | wrong |
| I don’t understand his language | - | correct |
| 2. He never talks Hausa | - | wrong |
| He does not speak Hausa | - | correct |
| 3. I am againsting the motion | - | wrong |
| I am opposing the motion | - | correct |
| 4. Adamu will return back tomorrow | - | wrong |
| Adamu will return tomorrow | - | correct |
| 5. I work under the Ministry of Education – | | wrong |
| I work in the polytechnics | - | correct |

Another obvious reason for students’ poor performance in English in general and M.A. in particular is the quantity and quality of teachers of English available in our schools. The background of some of the teachers in grammar themselves is as Olaofe (2013) puts it is very clear, slippery and weak. He goes on to suggest that:

The place of grammar in the teaching of English therefore, deserves a special attention, and effective handling of the conventional syntactic structures of the language is imperative for affective communication.

WAEC Chief Examiners have also lamented that a good number of candidates write very short essays irrelevant to the question and some time too long contrary to the expected length of 400 words for essay and 350 words for letter writing (chief examiners report (2020-2023)).

In the comprehension section the reports observed that some candidates would only engage in mindless lifting of portions of the passage which are irrelevant as answers to the questions.

Among others the reports suggested as remedies:

1. Wide reading by students
2. Adequate coverage of the course outline
3. Engaging students in drills in all the aspects in which poor performance manifested
4. Adequate background and exposure of candidates to the SSCE format and techniques of answering the questions.

Having identified some of the causes of this alarming poor performance in M.A. by candidates, it is only proper that a few suggestions are given to curb the problem:

4. Teachers should give greater attention to Mechanical areas that are more prone to giving problems to students. Students too, should make such areas their companions rather than their enemies.
5. The habit of proof-reading should particularly be inculcated in the students by teachers. However, it should be noted that in the final analysis it is the student who should take responsibility for eliminating mechanical errors. Bright and Megregor [1984] declares thus;
It does the pupil better to find five for himself than it does, if the teacher finds fifty.

Part B-Comprehension and Summary

Section .1 Comprehension

The section usually consists of two comprehension passages each followed by questions [usually seven]. The total marks allotted for the section is 40.

A part from questions that test understanding of the passage, questions that test the candidates understanding of grammatical structures and lexical items are included. Questions that test the ability of the candidate to recognise certain grammatical structures and how they function in the language have consistently been based on the following;

6. Parts of speech
7. Clauses/phrases
8. Idiomatic expressions
9. Figures of speech
10. Vocabulary

Unless otherwise stated answers in this section need not be in full sentences. However, candidates are penalized for any grammatical/expression errors made in each scoring answer by deducting ½ a mark. Thus, candidates should be advised to be brief and precise in answering questions in this section to minimize the number of mistakes they are likely to make. Similarly, where candidates give more than one answer to a question they stand the risk of scoring zero if one of the answers is wrong.

It is observed over the years that, like in part 'b' candidates lose a lot of marks in answering questions in the areas outlined above. Similarly, deductions as a result of grammatical errors and poor expression bring down the marks candidates score drastically. This further confirms the lack of mastery of the mechanics of English by students.

Section II Summary 30 Marks

This section usually consists of one passage followed by two or three questions.

If M.A. as an aspect, among the aspects, examiners consider in marking essay/letter writing is a matter of concern, more disturbing is the problem a whole section poses to candidates. In the summary section, out of the total marks allotted, a very significant number (who are courageous enough to attempt the section) score less than 10 marks on the average.

The following are some of the major problems that militate against students getting good marks in this section.

12. Blind lifting/copying
13. Including irrelevant/extraneous materials
14. In ability to write answers in full sentences
15. In ability to link preamble with answers to form full sentences
16. Poor expression and grammar
17. Giving more than one answer to a question

Penalties

Examiners penalise candidates for the following:

1. Deduction of ½ a mark for grammatical/expression errors in each scoring answer
2. Deduction of 1 mark for including irrelevant/extraneous material
3. Awarding zero to candidates who engage in mindless lifting
4. Deduction of ½ the total marks allotted to a question for lumping two answers together

CONCLUSION

The performance of the students in the English language examination is general and M.A. expression and summary in particular is very discouraging. They perform so woefully in these aspects that most of them get very low or no marks at all. Reasons for these have been highlighted and some precautionary measures given. There is therefore, the need to look inward in solving this rather disturbing phenomenon. This being so, the teacher's sound knowledge of grammatical structure as well as a good command of the language he teaches is of paramount importance. He should himself be able to distinguish between acceptable and unacceptable forms of the language.

In addition it is suggested that schools or even the Ministry of Education should encourage all teachers of English to attend at least the co-ordination meeting for examiners of English every time there is marking exercise. This will keep them abreast of the demands of the examination and further expose them to the acceptable and unacceptable forms of the language.

Teachers should also endeavor to continuously and in good time expose the students to the demands of the SSCE so that they are prepared and adequately kept well-informed of what they are expected to do to pass the examination as they might desire.

It is also hoped that the solutions this paper offers and other practical and legal measures taken by WAEC, government and school administrators would not only improve performance in English but curb the much talked – about examination malpractice ravaging the nations education system.

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